

Modular ML-Framework to develop and compare AI models for ARDS classification

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Abstract: Acute Respiratory Distress Syndrome (ARDS) is a severe condition in intensive care units with high mortality. The current standard for the diagnosis of ARDS is the Berlin-Definition. However, epidemiological studies have shown, that ARDS is often diagnosed too late or missed completely. Artificial Intelligence, i.e. machine learning or deep learning methods are proposed to help clinicians to identify ARDS earlier to improve the patient's outcome. In our work, we propose a modular machine learning framework for the development, comparison and use of AI models for ARDS classification.

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I. Introduction

Acute Respiratory Distress Syndrome (ARDS) is a severe inflammatory condition, that occurs in around 10 % of all mechanically ventilated patients in ICUs [1, 2]. Since 2012 the Berlin-Definition has been established as a standard for the diagnosis [3]. Even though there are clear criteria for the occurrence of an ARDS, the mortality rate is around 40 % for severe cases [2]. One reason for the high mortality is the under-recognition of ARDS, which impacts the patient management and outcome [2, 4]. To increase the detection rate of ARDS, artificial intelligence (AI), especially machine learning (ML) or deep learning (DL) methods are proposed to enable automatic monitoring of the recorded patient data [5]. The prediction of such models can be included into a Clinical Decision Support System (CDSS) and presented to the attending physician to support the decision-making process. Various AI methods have been published in the context of ARDS [6]. Nevertheless, there is still a big gap between the research and the clinical practice due to various factors, particularly insufficient model performance, lack of comparability or

reproducibility [7]. The latter is due to the fact that in many cases the data and code are not publicly available or the data preparation is not documented well enough. To address these challenges and to support the development of AI methods, we propose a Machine Learning Framework (MLF) that is tailored to ARDS classification.

II. Machine Learning Framework

The MLF is designed for the development and use of AI models. To cover different criteria of the Berlin-Definition, time series as well as image data models can be implemented (see Figure 1). Trained models can also be loaded into the framework in order to classify patient data and analyze it further (see Figure 2). The various process steps that can be configured for the respective workflow are described in the following.

1. Time-Series Data

Data quality plays a major role in the creation of AI models, as otherwise incorrect patterns may be learned and the results may be unreliable. To assess the quality of the data

Figure 1: Schematic representation of the process steps that are carried out with the Machine Learning Framework (MLF) in order to create AI models. Each step has individual configuration options and is modular in design.

used, quality metrics such as completeness, conformity and plausibility are specified for the time-series data [8]. Anomaly detection algorithms can also be used to identify erroneous data and remove it before training. Additional functions can be used to further prepare the data for learning an AI model. This allows the data to be filtered, e.g. to remove incorrect annotated patients, or select the most important parameters for training using different feature selection algorithms. Furthermore, as many algorithms cannot deal with missing values, various imputation methods are integrated into the framework to fill the gaps. The data set is subsequently divided into training data and test data. The model learner uses the pre-processed training data to train specified classifier(s) that are integrated into the framework. After training, the test data is used to calculate evaluation metrics, such as sensitivity, specificity and F1 score, and displayed to the user. After each modular step, the user has the option of visualizing the data and corresponding statistics in order to understand and analyze the process.

2. Image Data

The image data must also be processed before model training. The images are first transformed into a suitable format (such as pytorch files) and scaled to fit the integrated models, like e.g. a ResNet-50 [9]. Additionally, data augmentation is integrated in order to evaluate the robustness of the resulting DL models [10]. The image data set is split into training and test data and transferred to the model learner as well. Common explainable AI (xAI) methods such as SHAP or LIME can be used to analyze the performance of the model and interpret the results.

3. Use

To use trained AI models, patient data can be imported into the MLF. Here it is important that the user is provided with as much information as possible to make the model more comprehensible. Therefore, data and results of xAI methods are visualized. Finally, the results of the AI models are displayed so that a physician, for example, can take them into account in their diagnostic process.

III. Discussion

A major problem that we face in the healthcare sector is the low availability of data. There are hardly any data sets with the required data modalities or annotations available. Further research should collect explicit data for this

purpose, which can then be used as a basis for training AI models using the proposed MLF. When integrating a CDSS, regulations such as data protection and the Medical Devices Regulation must also be considered. An MLF, that makes the development process modular and recursive, can provide support here, as it enables the developer and user to understand how the model works and generate further insights. Furthermore, many process steps and results require an assessment by healthcare professionals, who should be integrated into the development process and be consulted regularly.

IV. Conclusions

Various AI models for the classification of ARDS have been published in literature and trained with different data sets. The proposed MLF is intended to support the comparability and development of future AI models by harmonizing the preparation steps and visualizing the results. We focus on the data analysis and explainability of the models in order to ensure comprehensibility. This aims to lay a foundation for the successful integration of a CDSS for ARDS classification in future studies.

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Figure 2: Schematic representation of the process steps that are carried out with the Machine Learning Framework (MLF) in order to use an AI model for the classification of ARDS and analyze the according model.